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**Dynamic changes in O-GlcNAcylation regulate osteoclast differentiation and bone loss
via nucleoporin 153**

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23 **Abstract**

24 Bone mass is maintained by the balance between osteoclast-induced bone resorption and oste-
25 oblast-triggered bone formation. In inflammatory arthritis such as rheumatoid arthritis (RA),
26 however, increased osteoclast differentiation and activity skew this balance resulting in pro-
27 gressive bone loss. O-GlcNAcylation is a posttranslational modification with attachment of a
28 single O-linked β -D-N-acetylglucosamine (O-GlcNAc) residue to serine or threonine residues
29 of target proteins. Although O-GlcNAcylation is one of the most common protein
30 modifications, its role in bone homeostasis has not been systematically investigated. We
31 demonstrate that dynamic changes in O-GlcNAcylation are required for osteoclastogenesis.
32 Increased O-GlcNAcylation promotes osteoclast differentiation during the early stages,
33 whereas its downregulation is required for osteoclast maturation. At the molecular level, O-
34 GlcNAcylation affects several pathways including oxidative phosphorylation and cell-cell
35 fusion. $\text{TNF}\alpha$ fosters the dynamic regulation of O-GlcNAcylation to promote
36 osteoclastogenesis in inflammatory arthritis. Targeted pharmaceutical or genetic inhibition of
37 O-GlcNAc transferase (OGT) or O-GlcNAcase (OGA) arrests osteoclast differentiation during
38 early stages of differentiation and during later maturation, respectively, and ameliorates bone
39 loss in experimental arthritis. Knockdown of NUP153, an O-GlcNAcylation target, has similar
40 effects as OGT inhibition and inhibits osteoclastogenesis. These findings highlight an important
41 role of O-GlcNAcylation in osteoclastogenesis and may offer the potential to therapeutically
42 interfere with pathologic bone resorption.

43 **Introduction**

44 Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is the most common chronic inflammatory joint disease affecting up
45 to 1% of the adult population. RA causes progressive joint destruction and leads to severe dis-
46 ability and reduced quality of life¹. Under physiologic conditions, bone mass is maintained by
47 constant remodeling with a balance between osteoclast-induced bone resorption and osteoblast-
48 triggered bone formation. However, in RA, this balance is shifted towards bone resorption
49 based on increased osteoclast differentiation, resulting in local and systemic bone loss².

50 Osteoclasts are macrophage polykaryons specialized on bone resorption³. Macrophage colony-
51 stimulating factor (M-CSF) and receptor activator of nuclear factor- κ B (NF- κ B) ligand
52 (RANKL) are key-regulators of osteoclastogenesis⁴⁻⁶. Proinflammatory cytokines such as tu-
53 mor necrosis factor alpha (TNF α) can further amplify osteoclast differentiation⁷⁻⁹. TNF α is a
54 key player in the pathogenesis of RA¹⁰. It is expressed abundantly in the synovium of inflamed
55 joints and stimulates osteoclastogenesis. This is exemplified by the phenotype of mice overex-
56 pressing human TNF α (hTNF α tg) that exhibit increased numbers of osteoclasts and develop
57 destructive arthritis, which resembles RA in humans¹¹. Moreover, targeted inhibition of TNF α
58 ameliorates inflammation and bone loss in patients with RA, has greatly improved the prognosis
59 of RA patients and is still the mainstay of RA treatment to date¹²⁻¹⁴.

60 O-GlcNAcylation involves covalent attachment of a single O-linked β -D-N-acetylglucosamine
61 (O-GlcNAc) residue to serine or threonine residues of proteins¹⁵. O-GlcNAcylation thereby
62 differs fundamentally from other forms of glycosylation that result in the attachment of large,
63 complex and often branched glycosyl-residues to target sites¹⁶. The level of O-GlcNAcylation
64 is regulated by only two enzymes: O-GlcNAc transferase (OGT), which is the only enzyme
65 capable of adding O-GlcNAc to target proteins, and O-GlcNAcase (OGA), which is essentially
66 required to remove O-GlcNAc¹⁷. O-GlcNAcylation is one of the most common protein modi-
67 fications¹⁸, but one only recently begins to appreciate its regulatory role in cellular homeostasis.

68 O-GlcNAcylation can alter the susceptibility of target proteins for other post-translational mod-
69 ifications, their subcellular localization, the association with binding partners, and affect protein
70 half-life^{19,20}. Via these mechanisms, O-GlcNAc can regulate central cellular events, such as
71 transcription, translation, intracellular trafficking, and differentiation¹⁷. Deregulation of O-Glc-
72 NAcylation has been implicated into the pathogenesis of chronic human diseases such as dia-
73 betes, cardiovascular diseases, neurodegeneration and cancer²¹. Of particular interest, O-Glc-
74 NAcylation can modulate inflammatory responses^{22,23}. We thus hypothesized that aberrant O-
75 GlcNAcylation may promote an inflammatory milieu that stimulates osteoclastogenesis in ar-
76 thritis.

77 In the present study, we characterized the role of O-GlcNAcylation in osteoclastogenesis. We
78 demonstrate a dynamic regulation of O-GlcNAcylation during osteoclastogenesis. Targeted in-
79 hibition of this dynamic balance in O-GlcNAcylation affects key regulators of osteoclastogen-
80 esis such as cytokine signaling, oxidative phosphorylation, organization of the actin cytoskele-
81 ton and cell-cell fusion and strongly inhibits osteoclastogenesis, in particular in the presence of
82 TNF α and in arthritis. Moreover, pharmaceutical inhibition of O-GlcNAcase or knockout of
83 OGT in the monocyte/macrophage lineage ameliorates inflammation as well as local and sys-
84 temic bone loss in preclinical models of RA.

85 **Results**

86 **Dynamic regulation of O-GlcNAcylation during osteoclastogenesis**

87 We first analyzed the levels of O-GlcNAcylation during the differentiation of osteoclast pre-
88 cursors into mature osteoclasts *in vitro*. O-GlcNAcylation progressively increased during the
89 early differentiation phase of osteoclastogenesis and peaked at around day 2. Thereafter, O-
90 GlcNAc levels progressively decreased in the maturation process with lowest levels in mature
91 multinucleated osteoclasts (**Fig. 1A**). Consistently, cellomics analysis showed that immature
92 TRAP and F4/80 double-positive (TRAP⁺F4/80⁺) osteoclasts had much higher levels of O-
93 GlcNAc compared to TRAP-positive, F4/80 negative (TRAP⁺F4/80⁻) mature osteoclasts (**Fig.**
94 **1B**).

95 We next analyzed the levels of O-GlcNAcylation in immature and mature osteoclasts in syno-
96 vial tissues of patients with RA and matched healthy individuals. Immunofluorescence staining
97 for O-GlcNAc demonstrated very high levels of O-GlcNAcylation in immature TRAP⁺CD14⁺
98 osteoclasts of RA patients and low levels in mature, multinucleated TRAP⁺CD14⁻ osteoclasts.
99 In healthy individuals, immature osteoclasts also stained for O-GlcNAc. However, confocal
100 microscopic analysis with semi-automated, blinded quantification showed that the levels of O-
101 GlcNAc in immature osteoclasts were lower as compared to those in RA patients (**Fig. 1C**).
102 Similar findings were observed in mice with transgenic overexpression of human TNF α
103 (hTNF α tg mice): TRAP⁺F4/80⁺ immature osteoclasts expressed very high levels of O-Glc-
104 NAcylation and decreased in TRAP⁺F4/80⁻ mature multinucleated osteoclasts. The levels of
105 O-GlcNAcylation in TRAP⁺F4/80⁺ immature osteoclast were higher in hTNF α tg mice than in
106 non-transgenic littermates (**Fig. 1D**).

107 Together, these findings highlight dynamic O-GlcNAcylation during osteoclastogenesis and
108 suggest that the inflammatory milieu in arthritis enhances O-GlcNAcylation. Consistent with
109 this hypothesis, costimulation of osteoclast precursors with TNF α and RANKL increased the
110 expression of OGT and OGA with higher ratios of OGT/OGA compared to RANKL only, and

111 induced in higher peak levels of O-GlcNAc without limiting its downregulation at later stages
112 (**Fig. 1E**). Indeed, cellomics analysis revealed that TNF α intensified the upregulation of O-
113 GlcNAc in immature osteoclasts with comparable levels of O-GlcNAc in mature osteoclasts
114 incubated with or without TNF α (**Supplementary Fig. 1**). Furthermore, the increase in the peak
115 levels of O-GlcNAcylation correlated with enhanced osteoclast differentiation in the presence
116 of TNF α as shown by cellomics analysis (**Fig. 1F**).

117

118 **Targeting OGT and early-stage increase in O-GlcNAcylation inhibits osteoclastogenesis**

119 To investigate the functional relevance of these dynamic changes in O-GlcNAcylation for os-
120 teoclast differentiation, we inhibited OGT during early stages of osteoclastogenesis using the
121 selective OGT inhibitor OSMI-1²⁴. Inhibition of OGT prevented the upregulation of O-Glc-
122 NAcylation during the early phase of osteoclastogenesis (**Fig. 2A, B**) which impaired the tran-
123 scription of *Nfatc1*, a master regulator of osteoclastogenesis²⁵⁻²⁷, and of *Acp5*, which encodes
124 for the osteoclast marker TRAP^{28,29} (**Fig. 2C**). OGT inhibition impaired osteoclastogenesis with
125 decreased numbers of immature and mature osteoclasts, reduced OC fusion index and decreased
126 TRAP activity (**Fig. 2D**). In contrast, OGT inhibition did not impair the proliferation of osteo-
127 clast precursors, indicating a specific effect on osteoclast differentiation and maturation (**Fig.**
128 **2E**). The inhibitory effects of OSMI-1 on osteoclastogenesis translated into impaired capacity
129 for bone resorption in *in vitro* assays (**Fig. 2F**).

130 To confirm these findings on the genetic level, we knocked out OGT in the monocytes lineage.
131 OGT knockout cells and control cells were isolated from the bone marrow of *Ogt*^{ALyM} mice
132 (mice with two conditional alleles of OGT (OGT^{fl/fl}) and LysM-Cre³⁰ expression) and OGT^{fl/fl}
133 littermates without LysM-Cre, respectively. OGT knockout reduced the levels of O-GlcNAcylation
134 (**Supplementary Fig. 2A, B**). OGT knockout cells had reduced levels of osteoclast-re-
135 lated genes *Nfatc1* and *Acp5* (**Supplementary Fig. 2C**) and demonstrated impaired potential
136 for osteoclast differentiation *in vitro* with reduced numbers of immature and mature osteoclasts,

137 decreased OC fusion, and lower TRAP activity (**Supplementary Fig. 2E**), but without notable
138 changes in proliferation (**Supplementary Fig. 2E**). OGT knockout cells also showed impaired
139 capacity for bone resorption in *in vitro* assays (**Supplementary Fig. 2F**). Together, these results
140 demonstrate that the upregulation of O-GlcNAcylation during early stages of differentiation is
141 essential for osteoclastogenesis.

142

143 **Targeting OGA and late-stage decrease of O-GlcNAcylation inhibits osteoclastogenesis**

144 We next investigated the functional relevance of the downregulation of O-GlcNAcylation in
145 later stages of osteoclastogenesis. We therefore inhibited OGA using the selective OGA inhib-
146 itor Thiamet-G³¹. Inhibition of OGA prevented the decrease of O-GlcNAcylation in the matu-
147 ration stage of osteoclastogenesis (**Fig. 3A, B**). This translated into functional arrest of osteo-
148 clastogenesis in the later stages, as shown by reduced mRNA levels of *Acp5*, but unchanged
149 levels of *Nfatc1*, which is upregulated in early stages of osteoclastogenesis (**Fig. 3C**). Impaired
150 downregulation of O-GlcNAcylation in later stages of osteoclastogenesis blocked maturation
151 of osteoclasts with reduced numbers of multinucleated mature osteoclasts, decreased OC fusion
152 index and TRAP activity, but did not affect proliferation (**Fig. 3D, E**). Consistent with the ki-
153 netics of O-GlcNAcylation with early increases and later downregulation, the number of im-
154 mature osteoclast precursors was not reduced by OGA inhibition. Thiamet-G reduced bone
155 degradation in *in vitro* resorption assays (**Fig. 3F**). In all experiments, modulation of O-Glc-
156 NAcylation had particularly pronounced inhibitory effects on osteoclastogenesis in the pres-
157 ence of TNF α with stronger effects as compared to osteoclastogenesis in the presence of
158 RANKL only (**Fig. 3**). These findings demonstrate that downregulation of O-GlcNAcylation in
159 later stages of osteoclastogenesis is functionally required for osteoclast maturation.

160 Next, we evaluated the outcome of osteoclastogenesis, when OSMI-1 and Thiamet-G were ap-
161 plied only during early stages of osteoclast differentiation. Two days of OSMI-1 treatment at
162 the early stages is sufficient to block the mature osteoclast formation. However, early-stage

163 OGA inhibition has limited effects in osteoclastogenesis (first two days; **Supplementary Fig.**
164 **3**). Under those experimental conditions, only OSMI-1, but not Thiamet-G inhibited osteoclas-
165 togenesis.

166

167 **Targeting O-GlcNAcylation by inhibition of OGT ameliorates inflammatory bone loss**

168 We next aimed to confirm the critical role of dynamic changes in O-GlcNAcylation for
169 osteoclastogenesis *in vivo*. We first targeted the increase in O-GlcNAcylation in early stages of
170 osteoclastogenesis by treatment of mice with serum-induced arthritis (SIA)³² with OSMI-1.
171 OSMI-1 treatment mitigated clinical symptoms of arthritis caused by the transfer of autoanti-
172 body-containing serum such as reduced grip strength and paw swelling (**Fig. 4A**). Treatment
173 with OSMI-1 also attenuated bone erosions in the paws as shown by the μ CT. OSMI-1 amelio-
174 rated not only local bone erosion but also systemic osteoporosis, as shown by quantification of
175 bone volume density in the tibia bones (**Fig. 4B**). Histological analysis demonstrated less in-
176 flammation, reduced bone erosions, and decreased numbers of both, immature and mature os-
177 teoclasts by OSMI-1 treatment. Immunofluorescence further demonstrated reduced O-Glc-
178 NAcylation levels in OSMI-1 treated mice (**Fig. 4C**).

179 We confirmed these findings by LysM-Cre driven knockout of OGT in osteoclast precursor
180 cells in hTNF α tg mice³⁰ using bone marrow transplantation. Knockout of OGT in osteoclast
181 precursors prevented inflammation-induced osteoclastogenesis, ameliorated local and systemic
182 bone loss, and reduced joint inflammation (**Supplementary Fig. 4A, B**). Consistent with the
183 findings in OSMI-1 treated mice, OGT knockout in hTNF α tg mice abrogated the increase in
184 O-GlcNAcylation and the accumulation of immature and mature osteoclasts in arthritic mice
185 (**Supplementary Fig. 4C**).

186 A recent study showed that O-GlcNAcylation could affect immune responses in macrophages³³.
187 To exclude that the observed effects on osteoclastogenesis in arthritis models are mediated in-
188 directly by modulation of inflammation, we next tested the role of O-GlcNAcylation in a model
189 with less inflammatory involvement, the ovariectomy-induced osteoporosis (OVX). Indeed,
190 OGT knockdown in monocytic cells did not change leukocyte infiltration into the synovium in
191 the OVX model. However, consistent with the findings in the hTNF α tg and SIA models, OGT
192 knockout in osteoclasts precursors mitigates OVX-induced bone loss and reduces the number
193 of mature osteoclasts (**Supplementary Fig. 5**).

194 Together, these findings demonstrate that the upregulation of O-GlcNAcylation in early stages
195 of differentiation is essential for osteoclastogenesis and osteoclast-mediated bone resorption in
196 inflammatory and non-inflammatory models of bone loss.

197

198 **Inhibition of the downregulation of O-GlcNAcylation reduces osteoclastogenesis in** 199 **experimental arthritis**

200 We next targeted the downregulation of O-GlcNAcylation in late stages of osteoclastogenesis
201 by inhibition of OGA with Thiamet-G in hTNF α tg mice. Treatment with Thiamet-G amelio-
202 rated loss of grip strength and paw swelling (**Fig. 5A**), reduced local and systemic bone loss
203 with decreased local erosions and systemic osteoporosis (**Fig. 5B**). Treatment with Thiamet-G
204 also reduced synovial inflammation, increased the levels of O-GlcNAcylation, and reduced the
205 formation of mature osteoclasts without affecting the number of immature osteoclasts (**Fig.**
206 **5C**).

207 We also analyzed the effects of Thiamet-G in the SIA model. Treatment with Thiamet-G re-
208 duced clinical signs of arthritis, ameliorated local and systemic bone loss, and decreased the
209 numbers of mature osteoclasts without reducing the number of immature osteoclasts (**Supple-**
210 **mentary Fig. 6**).

211 Together, these data highlight that a dynamic regulation of O-GlcNAcylation is critically re-
212 quired for osteoclastogenesis and osteoclast-mediated bone loss.

213

214 **Differential, stage-specific transcriptional effects of OGT- and OGA-inhibition**

215 We next aimed to characterize the molecular mechanisms by which O-GlcNAc regulates oste-
216 oclastogenesis. We therefore performed RNA sequencing of osteoclast precursors incubated
217 with M-CSF, RANKL and TNF α with inhibition of OGT at early stages by OSMI-1, with inhi-
218 bition of OGA at later stages by Thiamet-G and controls with M-CSF, RANKL, TNF α and
219 vehicle or with M-CSF and vehicle only. Principal component analysis (PCA) demonstrated
220 that OSMI-1 inhibited osteoclastogenesis at very early stages with transcriptional profiles most
221 closely related to precursors incubated with M-CSF only. In contrast, Thiamet-G arrested oste-
222 oclastogenesis at later stages with more similarities to cells incubated to M-CSF, RANKL and
223 TNF α (**Fig. 6A**). To further characterize the effects at different stages, we generated a gene set
224 containing genes regulated at different stages of osteoclastogenesis from publically available
225 datasets^{34,35}. Expression heatmaps of the gene set further highlights that OSMI-1 and Thiamet-
226 G exert stage-specific effects and that the most osteoclast-related genes are regulated by O-
227 GlcNAcylation (**Fig. 6B and Supplementary Fig. 7**).

228 After application of cutoffs compared to controls, we identified 1865 differentially expressed
229 genes (DEGs) in OSMI-1 treated cells and 1565 DEGs in Thiamet-G treated cells (**Fig. 6C, E**).
230 Consistent with the potent inhibitory effects on osteoclastogenesis *in vitro* and *in vivo*, geneset
231 enrichment analysis (GSEA) demonstrated negative enrichment scores (“de-enrichment”) for
232 genes related to osteoclast differentiation³⁶ for OSMI-1 and Thiamet-G (**Fig. 6D, F**). Using
233 gene functional analysis for Gene Ontology (GO) biological processes, we found profound
234 enrichment of categories relevant for osteoclastogenesis for OSMI-1 and Thiamet-G. However,
235 the individual categories demonstrated differences and OSMI-1 affected in particular categories
236 required for early steps of osteoclast differentiation such as cytokine signaling, leukocyte

237 differentiation and metabolic adaptation (**Fig. 6G**), whereas Thiamet-G regulated in particular
238 categories implicated in later maturation stages such as cell-cell fusion, rearrangement of the
239 actin cytoskeleton, integrin-mediated cellular adhesion and bone remodelling (**Fig. 6H**). GSEA
240 pathway enrichment analysis further confirmed the regulation of multiple categories implicated
241 in different stages of osteoclastogenesis by OSMI-1 and Thiamet-G (**Supplementary Fig. 8A,**
242 **B**).

243 Moreover, our data obtained from OSMI-1 and Thiamet-G treated murine osteoclast precursors
244 both showed distinct, but highly significant association patterns with considerable enrichment
245 scores for genes deregulated in human macrophages obtained from synovial fluid of inflamed
246 joints from patients with RA (**Supplementary Fig. 8C, D**). These results demonstrate that O-
247 GlcNAcylation regulates the transcription of core genes and pathways required for inflamma-
248 tion-induced osteoclastogenesis. We next aimed to unravel upstream transcription regulators
249 are capable of regulating the expression of O-GlcNAc-dependent DEGs. Using Ingenuity Path-
250 way Analysis (IPA) with thresholds of $|\text{activation z-score}| > 2$ and p-value of overlap < 0.001 ,
251 we identified 11 potential transcription regulators of the DEGs in OSMI-1 treated cells (**Sup-**
252 **plementary Fig. 9A**). Since O-GlcNAcylation is a post-translational modification, we were
253 particularly interested in the regulators without transcriptional changes upon OSMI-1 treatment.
254 These included several well-known transcriptional regulators of osteoclastogenesis (**Supple-**
255 **mentary Fig. 9B**). Amongst those, MYC (which was recently identified as a key regulator of
256 osteoclastogenesis^{37,38}) was proposed to regulate the largest subset of OSMI-DEGs (108 genes)
257 and demonstrated as the most significant target in the two analyses for motif enrichment on
258 OSMI-DEGs (**Supplementary Fig. 9C**). GSEA analysis demonstrated downregulation of
259 MYC target genes in osteoclast precursors upon OGT inhibition (**Supplementary Fig. 9D**).
260 We matched our RNA-Seq results obtained from osteoclast precursors with OGT inhibition to
261 a dataset of osteoclast precursors with MYC knockout³⁸. We observed a 78.6% overlap in the

262 enriched GO biological process (**Supplementary Fig. 9E**). These results support our hypothe-
263 sis on the role of MYC in O-GlcNAc-dependent osteoclastogenesis.

264

265 **Inhibition of O-GlcNAc target nucleoporin 153 (NUP153) disrupts osteoclastogenesis**

266 We next aimed to identify proteins that are differentially O-GlcNAcylated during early stages
267 of osteoclastogenesis using mass spectrometry as an unbiased screening approach. Incubation
268 of osteoclast precursor cells with RANKL and TNF α for 3 days induced O-GlcNAcylation of
269 functionally heterogeneous target proteins including the nuclear pore component NUP153, the
270 MTDH (also known as Metadherin, LYRIC or astrocyte elevated gene-1 protein (AEG-1)) as a
271 regulator of RNA splicing³⁹, IFI207 as a transcriptional regulator of innate immune responses⁴⁰
272 and RBM27, involved in mRNA decay⁴¹. Most pronounced differences were observed for
273 NUP153, with 7.7 fold increased upon RANKL and TNF α costimulation compared to controls.
274 To provide evidence for a functional role of those O-GlcNAcylated proteins in osteoclastogen-
275 esis, we evaluated the potential of these O-GlcNAcylated proteins to regulate the O-GlcNAc-
276 driven transcriptome. Therefore, we integrated mass spectrometry findings with the results of
277 our RNASeq experiments. Using IPA, we predicted the capability of the O-GlcNAcylated pro-
278 teins detected by mass spectrometry to serve as upstream regulators for DEGs identified by
279 RNASeq in OSMI-1 treated samples. IPA proposed interactions between NUP153 and the tran-
280 scription factor MYC, which had been predicted as the most potent upstream regulator of O-
281 GlcNAc-DEGs in our RNASeq experiments. NUP153 has also been shown to regulate the nu-
282 clear transport of MYC⁴². This suggests a model, in which O-GlcNAcylation-induced changes
283 in the activity of NUP153 may modify the nuclear activity of these transcription factors to reg-
284 ulate the expression of osteoclastogenic genes. Based on its most pronounced differences in O-
285 GlcNAcylation levels and on its potential to regulate target genes of O-GlcNAcylation, we thus
286 focused on NUP153 as an effector for O-GlcNAcylation-regulated osteoclastogenesis for our
287 further studies (**Supplementary Fig. 10**).

288 We first confirmed increased O-GlcNAcylation of NUP153 during early stages of RANKL /
289 TNF α -induced osteoclastogenesis by immunoprecipitation. Consistent with global O-GlcNAc
290 dynamics, the O-GlcNAcylation of NUP153 decreased at later stages of osteoclastogenesis
291 (**Fig. 7A**). Further analyses of the mass spectrometry data demonstrated that O-GlcNAcylation
292 was only detected at T546 and S548 of NUP153 in RANKL and TNF α costimulated precursors,
293 but not at other putative sites (**Fig. 7B**).

294 Consistent with the proposed mode of action, knockdown of *Nup153* decreased the nuclear
295 accumulation of MYC upon RANKL and TNF α costimulation (**Fig. 7C, D and Supplemen-**
296 **tary Fig. 11A**). To verify the functional role of NUP153 in osteoclastogenesis, we knockdown
297 *Nup153* during osteoclast differentiation by siRNA. We found that *Nup153* knockdown de-
298 creased *Nfatc1* and *Acp5* mRNA levels (**Supplementary Fig. 11B**). Knockdown of *Nup153*
299 also lowered the percentage of immature and mature osteoclast, OC fusion index, and TRAP
300 activity (**Fig. 7E and Supplementary Fig. 11C**), thus mimicking the findings of OSMI treat-
301 ment during early stages of osteoclastogenesis. *In vitro* bone resorption assays demonstrated
302 impaired pit formation in cells treated with *Nup153* siRNA compared to control siRNA (**Sup-**
303 **plementary Fig. 11D**). Together, these results demonstrate that the O-GlcNAc target NUP153
304 regulates the nuclear translocation and thus the transcriptional activity of MYC to control the
305 expression of osteoclast differentiation genes and promote osteoclast differentiation *in vitro*
306 (**Fig. 7F**).

307

308 **Discussion**

309 We demonstrate that osteoclast differentiation requires a dynamic regulation of O-GlcNAcylation
310 with increasing levels during early stage and progressive decline to baseline levels in late
311 stage of osteoclastogenesis. Interference with the upregulation of O-GlcNAcylation during
312 early stage induces an arrest in osteoclast differentiation characterized by profound transcrip-
313 tional inhibition of cytokine signaling and prevention of metabolic adaptation in differentiating

314 cells. Inhibition of the downregulation of O-GlcNAc in late stages of osteoclastogenesis by
315 inhibition of OGA also blocks osteoclastogenesis. The mechanisms accounting for those later
316 effects are different and include inhibition of rearrangement of the actin cytoskeleton and of
317 osteoclast fusion. Inhibition of OGT in early stages of differentiation is sufficient to impair the
318 formation of mature osteoclasts, whereas inhibition of OGA during the early stages has no sig-
319 nificant effects on osteoclast numbers. These findings demonstrate that O-GlcNAcylation con-
320 trols multiple different cellular processes to regulate osteoclastogenesis in a stage-dependent
321 manner.

322 The upregulation of OGT mRNA in osteoclastogenic conditions was blocked by p38 inhibition,
323 but not by inhibition of Erk, Src, cJUN/AP1. This result points to a p38-dependent regulation
324 of O-GlcNAcylation in early phases of osteoclast differentiation. However, we did not observe
325 shifts in the ratio of OGT and OGA levels in favor of OGA in late stages of osteoclastogenesis.
326 The regulation of OGA may thus occur on the levels of its enzymatic activity rather on the level
327 of transcription or translation. Indeed, several factors have been shown to affect OGA activity
328 and stability, such as the interaction with OGT at Ser405⁴³, Tax protein binding⁴⁴, nuclear lo-
329 calization upon nucleolar stress⁴⁵, or cellular redox balance⁴⁶. Cellular redox environment and
330 nucleolar function have been shown to be involved in osteoclastogenesis^{47,48}. However, eluci-
331 dation of the detailed regulation of OGA activity in osteoclasts requires further studies.

332 The induction of *Nfatc1* by RANKL can be separated into two phases: an initial induction by
333 NFATc2 and NF- κ B and later auto-amplification of NFATc1 by self-amplifying mechanisms²⁶.
334 Our transcriptome data showed that OGT inhibition blocked *Nfatc1* induction without affecting
335 the expression of p65, p50, and I κ B α . This results provides preliminary evidence that O-Glc-
336 NAcylation rather modulate the auto-amplification of *Nfatc1* than its initial NF- κ B-dependent
337 induction. However, the mechanism of O-GlcNAc-regulated *Nfatc1* expression requires further
338 studies.

339 Our study shows that TNF α , a key mediator of inflammation in arthritis, fosters the dynamic
340 regulation of O-GlcNAcylation during osteoclastogenesis. TNF α increases the expression lev-
341 els of OGT and OGA to promote enhanced osteoclastogenesis in early stages without affecting
342 its downregulation in later stages. Other proinflammatory cytokines such as IL-1 or metabolic
343 adaptations may also contribute to this early upregulation of O-GlcNAcylation^{49,50}. However, the
344 mechanisms coordinating the biphasic regulation of O-GlcNAcylation with downregulation
345 during later stages of osteoclastogenesis require further studies. Consistent with this regulatory
346 effect of TNF α on O-GlcNAcylation, inhibition of O-GlcNAcylation was particularly effective
347 when osteoclast precursors were cultured in the presence of TNF α . Together, these findings
348 provide evidence that TNF α regulates O-GlcNAylation to promote excessive osteoclastogene-
349 sis in inflammatory arthritis including RA in humans.

350 Our study highlights that interference with the dynamic regulation of O-GlcNAcylation can be
351 employed as a strategy to target aberrant osteoclastogenesis. Pharmacologic inhibition of OGT
352 by OSMI-1 or monocyte-specific knockout of OGT inhibits osteoclastogenesis by blocking
353 early transcriptional events of osteoclastogenesis. Although the molecular mechanisms of ac-
354 tion are different, targeting of OGA by Thiamet-G arrests osteoclast differentiation and fusions,
355 thereby preventing the formation of mature osteoclasts. Both treatments strongly reduce the
356 accumulation of mature osteoclasts with prevention of local bone erosions in the inflamed joints
357 as well as amelioration of systemic, inflammation-induced bone loss. O-GlcNAcylation has
358 also been reported to regulate osteoblastic differentiation of the MC3T3-E1 cell line⁵¹. How-
359 ever, differentiation of MC3T3-E1 cells requires no dynamic regulation, but constantly increas-
360 ing levels of O-GlcNAcylation. While Thiamet-G may thus in part increase bone density by
361 fostering osteoblast differentiation, targeting of OGT would rather inhibit osteoblast function.
362 Potential effects on osteoblasts are thus insufficient to explain the findings obtained with OGT
363 and OGA modulation in our arthritis models.

364 Mechanistically, O-GlcNAcylation may simultaneously regulate several core pathways of os-
365 teoclastogenesis in a NUP153-dependent manner. IPA suggested MYC as the most potent up-
366 stream regulator of OGT target genes. A recent study proposed MYC as a central component
367 driving the regulatory gene network for osteoclast-lineage commitment³⁷. MYC has also been
368 shown to trigger metabolic reprogramming during osteoclast differentiation³⁸. Our GO and
369 GSEA analysis showed metabolism-related pathways are highly enriched in the OGT inhibited
370 transcriptome. The unaltered transcription levels of MYC upon OGT inhibition together with
371 the absence in mass spectrometry analysis indicate an indirect regulation of their activity via
372 another target protein. Indeed, our newly identified O-GlcNAcylation target NUP153 is capable
373 of interacting with MYC⁴². NUP153 is known to control nucleoplasmic trafficking and regulate
374 gene expression by direct binding with chromatin and transcription factors⁵². Indeed, we
375 demonstrate that knockdown of *Nup153* impairs nuclear translocation and chromatin binding
376 of MYC. Consistently, osteoclast precursor cells were arrested at similar differentiation status
377 with comparable functional deficits upon OGT inhibition and upon *Nup153* knockdown. Data
378 mining of RNASeq results from osteoclast precursors with MYC knockout also supports an O-
379 GlcNAc-dependent regulation of MYC. O-GlcNAcylation is also known to regulate transcrip-
380 tional events by direct modification of transcription factors. Examples include O-GlcNAc-in-
381 duced changes in the stability of c-Jun in HEK 293T cells⁵³, as well as O-GlcNAc-induced
382 changes in the transcriptional activities of NF- κ B and NFATc1 in lymphocytes⁵⁴. Further stud-
383 ies are required to analyze the potential roles of other O-GlcNAcylated proteins in osteoclasto-
384 genesis and how they may synergize with NUP153 to regulate osteoclastogenesis. Our IPA
385 analysis on RNA-Seq data of osteoclast precursors treated with Thiamet-G indicated deregula-
386 tion of several pathways relevant for osteoclast maturation, such as CREBBP, IRF/STAT, and
387 MAFB. Haploinsufficient CREBBP mice displayed osteoporotic phenotype with hyper-active
388 osteoclastogenesis⁵⁵. Enhanced osteoclast fusion was observed in IRF1- or STAT1-knockout
389 cells⁵⁶. MAFB is also known as a negative regulator for osteoclast differentiation⁵⁷. The role of

390 O-GlcNAcylation for the regulation of these pathways requires further experimental validation.
391 Although further experiments are required for confirmation, these findings indicate that the
392 effects of O-GlcNAcylation on osteoclast differentiation might be mediated by O-GlcNAcylation-induced differences in NUP153 activity with deregulation of the nuclear access of MYC.
393
394 In addition to impaired osteoclastogenesis and preservation of bone integrity, we observed anti-inflammatory effects in hTNF α tg and SIA models with pharmacological inhibition and also
395 with monocyte-specific inactivation of OGT. O-GlcNAcylation has previously been shown to
396 stimulate the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines from synovial fibroblasts in Nf κ B-dependent manner²². The anti-inflammatory effects of pharmacological modulation of O-GlcNAc may
397 thus at least in part dependent on impaired cytokine release from synovial fibroblasts. However,
398 the finding that targeted inactivation of OGT in monocytic cells also strongly ameliorates synovial inflammation highlights that monocyte-lineage cells are also targeted by the anti-inflammatory effects of O-GlcNAc in experimental arthritis. This conclusion is further supported by
399 our findings that multiple GO- and GESA-terms related to cytokine signaling and inflammation are regulated by O-GlcNAcylation in osteoclast precursors. Although pro-inflammatory in our
400 murine models of arthritis, the role of O-GlcNAcylation in inflammatory conditions is complex and cell type dependent^{58,59}. Both pro- and anti-inflammatory effects have also been reported
401 in certain settings, e.g. by MAVS-dependent enhancement of anti-viral immunity⁶⁰, by RIPK3-dependent suppression of necroptosis in sepsis⁶¹, and involvement in both Treg and Th17 development^{15,62}. The effects of targeted modulation of O-GlcNAcylation on inflammation in arthritis thus deserve further studies. However, we also provide evidence that the regulatory effects of O-GlcNAcylation are not exclusively mediated indirectly by modulation of inflammation: 1.) interference with the dynamic regulation of O-GlcNAc also blocked osteoclastogenesis *in vitro*; 2.) inactivation of OGT also ameliorated osteoclast formation and bone loss in the
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414 OVX model, as a less inflammatory model of bone loss.

415 In summary, we demonstrate that O-GlcNAcylation regulates several critical pathways of os-
416 teoclastogenesis. Initial increases in O-GlcNAc promote cytokine signaling and metabolic ad-
417 aptation to promote differentiation of osteoclast precursors, while downregulation of O-Glc-
418 NAc in later stages stimulates rearrangement of the actin cytoskeleton and enhances cell-cell
419 fusion to promote osteoclast maturation. Interference with the dynamic regulation of O-Glc-
420 NAcylation by different pharmacologic or genetic approaches blocks osteoclast differentiation
421 and ameliorates local and systemic bone loss in arthritis.

422 **Material and methods**

423 **Patient recruitment**

424 Synovial tissues were obtained from ten RA patients with a disease duration of 1.5 – 27 years
425 and seropositive, erosive RA. All RA patients fulfilled the 2010 American College of
426 Rheumatology (ACR) classification criteria for RA⁶³. Tissue samples from matched healthy
427 donors were included for the comparison.

428

429 **Mice**

430 Wildtype male C57BL/6JRj mice were supplied by Janvier Labs (Saint-Berthevin, France).
431 Transgenic mice that overexpressed human TNF α (hTNF α tg)^{64,65}, *Ogt*-floxed⁶⁶, and *LysM*-
432 Cre^{30,65} (The Jackson Laboratory, Bar Harbor, ME, USA) have been described previously. To
433 knockout *Ogt* in myeloid lineage cells, we generated *Ogt*^{ALysM} mice by cross-breeding *Ogt*-
434 floxed and *LysM*-Cre. We used *Ogt*-floxed mice as littermate control for all the *Ogt* knockout
435 experiments.

436

437 **Bone marrow isolation and *in vitro* osteoclastogenesis**

438 *In vitro* osteoclastogenesis was performed as previously described^{38,67} with minor modifica-
439 tions. In brief, bone marrow cells from 8 to 12-week old wildtype, *Ogt*-floxed, or *Ogt*^{ALysM} mice
440 were harvested by flushing the tibia and femur of mice with α -MEM (Gibco, New York, USA),
441 followed by the lysis of red blood cells with RBC lysis buffer (Biolegend, San Diego, CA,
442 USA). Afterwards, cells were cultured in in 10% FBS α -MEM overnight. The non-adherent
443 cells were then seeded at the density of 2.5×10^5 cells/ mL and expanded with 25 ng/mL M-
444 CSF (R&D Systems, Wiesbaden-Nordenstadt, Germany) for 3 days. Osteoclastogenesis was
445 induced with 25 ng/mL M-CSF, 50 ng/mL RANKL (Peprotech, Hamburg, Germany) with or
446 without 20 ng/mL TNF α (R&D Systems) for 4 days. The culture medium was changed every 2
447 days.

448 **Cellomics and TRAP activity for *in vitro* osteoclastogenesis**

449 Cells were fixed in 4% formaldehyde and permeabilized in 0.2% Triton X-100 after 2 days
450 (immature phase) or 4 days (mature phase) of *in vitro* osteoclastogenesis. After blocking with
451 5% horse serum in 2% BSA/PBS, cells were incubated with antibodies against F4/80 (Bio-Rad,
452 Feldkirchen, Germany; clone Cl:A3-1) and O-GlcNAc (Invitrogen, Darmstadt, Germany, clone
453 RL2). Corresponding Alexa Fluor-conjugated secondary antibodies and the dye HCS CellMask
454 Deep Red Stain (both from Invitrogen) were used for detection of primary antibodies and for
455 cytosol/nucleus staining, respectively. TRAP activity was visualized using a leukocyte acid
456 phosphatase staining kit (Sigma-Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany) with ELF 97 Phosphatase Sub-
457 strate (Invitrogen) as described⁶⁸. Images and cellomics data were acquired by using a CellIn-
458 sight CX5 High Content Screening Platform with SpotDetector.V4 BioApplication (Thermo
459 Scientific, Darmstadt, Germany). For cells derived from bone marrow, TRAP⁺F4/80⁺ cells with
460 a single nucleus were identified as immature osteoclasts⁶⁹. TRAP⁺F4/80⁻ cells with more than
461 3 nuclei were identified as mature osteoclasts. For cells derived from RAW264.7, immature
462 and mature osteoclasts were identified by TRAP activity and nucleus count. Cellomics data
463 were analyzed using the R software (version 3.6.1) with custom codes, and the images were
464 processed by ImageJ software (NIH, version 1.52p).

465

466 **Western blot analysis and ProteinSimple Wes immunoassay**

467 Whole cell lysates from *in vitro* osteoclastogenesis were collected with Cell Lysis Buffer (Cell
468 Signaling Technology, Frankfurt am Main, Germany). Western blots were performed as de-
469 scribed previously⁷⁰. Briefly, protein was separated by SDS-PAGE and transferred onto an Im-
470 mobilon-P membrane (Millipore, Darmstadt, Germany). The membrane was incubated with
471 antibodies against O-GlcNAc (Invitrogen, clone RL2), NFATc1 (Biolegend, clone 7A6), and
472 β -actin (Sigma-Aldrich, clone AC-15) overnight. The blot was visualized with corresponding
473 horseradish peroxidase-conjugated antibodies (Dako, Glostrup, Denmark) and Amersham ECL

474 Prime Western Blotting Detection Reagent (Cytiva, Freiburg, Germany) and a ChemiDoc MP
475 Imaging System (Bio-Rad Laboratories). The images of the bots were analyzed with Image Lab
476 software (Bio-Rad Laboratories, version 6.0.1).

477 ProteinSimple Wes immunoassay was performed as described⁷¹ and analyzed by using a Wes
478 system (ProteinSimple, Wiesbaden, Germany) with antibodies against OGT (OriGene Tech-
479 nologies, Herford, Germany), OGA (Sigma-Aldrich), and β -actin.

480

481 **Histological and immunofluorescence (IF) analysis of synovial tissue**

482 The histomorphometric analysis was performed as described previously⁷². Hind legs from mice
483 were fixed in 4% formaldehyde and dehydrated in 50% ethanol, followed by decalcification in
484 500 mM acid-free EDTA and paraffin-embedding. Five μ m sections of paws were stained with
485 H&E for histology and TRAP for the quantification of the area of bone erosions and osteoclast
486 counts using a leukocyte acid phosphatase staining kit (Sigma-Aldrich). Mature osteoclasts
487 were identified as TRAP-positive multinucleated (nuclei ≥ 3) cells and the immature osteoclasts
488 as TRAP-positive cells with a single nucleus. Images were captured using a Nikon Eclipse 80i
489 microscope (Nikon Metrology, Alzenau, Germany) or a NanoZoomer S60 Digital Slide Scan-
490 ner (Hamamatsu Photonics, Herrsching am Ammersee, Germany).

491 The IF analysis was performed as described⁷³. Briefly, paw sections were deparaffinized and
492 rehydrated, followed by heat-induced epitope retrieval using boiling 10 mM sodium citrate pH
493 6.0 buffer and Tris-EDTA buffer (10 mM Tris, 1 mM EDTA, 0.05% Tween-20, pH 9.0). After
494 blocking with 5% horse serum in 2% BSA/PBS, sections were incubated with antibodies against
495 TRAP (Abcam, Berlin, Germany; clone EPR15556 for human tissue; Abnova, Taipei City, Tai-
496 wan; polyclonal for mouse tissue), CD14 (Biorbyt, Eching, Germany; polyclonal for human
497 tissue), F4/80 (Bio-Rad Laboratories, clone Cl:A3-1 for mouse tissue), and O-GlcNAc (Invi-
498 trogen, clone RL2), followed by alexa fluor-conjugated secondary antibodies (Invitrogen). Con-
499 focal images were acquired by using a Leica SP5 II confocal laser scanning microscope (Leica

500 Microsystems, Wetzlar, Germany), and processed with the same contrast adjustment for com-
501 parison by using OMERO web platform (University of Dundee & Open Microscopy Environ-
502 ment, version 5.6.3). The quantification of O-GlcNAc in TRAP-positive cells on the articular
503 surface of the tarsus was performed by measuring mean gray value of O-GlcNAc staining
504 within semi-automatically generated region based on TRAP signal using ImageJ software
505 (NIH, version 1.52p) for unbiased quantification.

506

507 **Quantitative real-time PCR**

508 Quantification of gene expression by quantitative real-time PCR was performed as described⁷⁴.
509 Briefly, RNA was isolated using a NucleoSpin RNA isolation kit (Macherey-Nagel, Düren,
510 Germany). After reverse transcription, cDNA was mixed with SYBRGreen PCR Master Mix
511 (Applied Biosystems, Darmstadt, Germany) and primer pairs described at **Supplementary Ta-**
512 **ble 1**. Gene expression was quantified using the comparative CT method with *Actb* as a house
513 keeping gene. Real-time PCR was performed using StepOnePlus Real-Time PCR System (Ap-
514 plied Biosystems). The data were analyzed with StepOne Software v2.3 (Applied Biosystems).

515

516 **Quantification of the number of metabolically active cells**

517 The number of metabolically active cells was determined using the Cell Counting Kit-8 (CCK-
518 8, Sigma-Aldrich) following the instruction from the supplier. In brief, the CCK-8 reagent was
519 added to the cells after 3 days of *in vitro* osteoclastogenesis for 2 hours. Then the absorbance
520 at 450 nm was measured by using a GloMax Discover Microplate Reader (Promega, Walldorf,
521 Germany). The number of metabolically active cells was calculated using a standard curve gen-
522 erated by serial dilution of cell number when seeding.

523

524

525

526 ***In vitro* bone resorption assay**

527 The bone resorption assays were performed as previously described⁷⁵. In brief, bone marrow
528 cells from mice were seeded on bone slices (Immunodiagnostic Systems, Frankfurt am Main,
529 Germany) with cytokines for *in vitro* osteoclastogenesis and with or without 20 μ M OSMI-1
530 (Sigma-Aldrich) or 10 μ M Thiamet-G (Tocris, Wiesbaden-Nordenstadt, Germany). The culture
531 medium was changed every 2 days for 2 weeks. The resorption pits were visualized by staining
532 with 1% toluidine blue (Sigma-Aldrich). Images were acquired using a Nikon Eclipse 80i mi-
533 croscope (Nikon Metrology) and then analyzed with ImageJ software (NIH, version 1.52p).

534

535 **Arthritis mouse models and *in vivo* treatments**

536 hTNF α tg mice spontaneously develop chronic inflammatory arthritis⁶⁴. For OGA inhibition,
537 hTNF α tg mice were injected with 6 mg/kg Thiamet-G (Tocris) intraperitoneally (i.p.) every
538 other day, starting at the age of four weeks. To knockout *Ogt* in the osteoclast precursors, bone
539 marrow transplantation was performed as described¹¹. In brief, four-week-old wildtype or
540 hTNF α tg mice received total body irradiation at the dose of 10.5 Gy. After 24 hours, the irra-
541 diated mice were transplanted with bone marrow cells from *Ogt*-floxed or *Ogt*^{ALysM} mice by tail
542 vein injection. The mice were euthanized at the age of nine weeks.

543 Serum-induced arthritis (SIA) was induced by injection of pooled serum from K/BxN mice as
544 described⁷². Arthritis was initiated in mice at the age of eight weeks by i.p. injection of 200 μ L
545 K/BxN serum and boosted with the same amount of serum three days later. To inhibit OGT or
546 OGA, mice were injected i.p. with 10 mg/kg OSMI-1 (Sigma-Aldrich) or 6 mg/kg Thiamet-G
547 (Tocris), respectively, every other day. Mice were euthanized 14 days after the first serum in-
548 jection.

549 Ovariectomy (OVX) -induced osteoporosis was performed by surgical removal of bilateral ova-
550 raries⁷⁵. Female *Ogt*-floxed and *Ogt*^{ALysM} mice were used to evaluate the effect of O-GlcNAc in
551 osteoporosis. OVX and sham operation, in which ovaries were left intact, were performed when

552 the mice reached 8 weeks of age. Mice were kept for five weeks after the operation before
553 euthanization.

554 The development of arthritis was evaluated by measuring joint swelling at the paws and the
555 grip strength of the mice as described⁷⁵. Bone tissues from the hind legs of the mice were har-
556 vested for further analysis. All studies were approved by the government of Unterfranken, Ger-
557 many.

558

559 **Microcomputed tomography (μ CT) and analysis**

560 μ CT analysis was performed as previously described⁷⁶. Bones of tibiae and paws from mice
561 were preserved in 50% ethanol. μ CT images were acquired using a SCANCO Medical μ CT 40
562 scanner (SCANCO Medical AG, Brüttisellen, Switzerland) with optimized settings for visual-
563 ization of calcified tissue at 55 kVp at a current of 145 μ A and 200 ms integration time for 500
564 projections/180°. The trabecular measurements were performed at a 1680 μ m region located
565 around 400 μ m below the middle of the tibia metaphysis. The volume segmentation for the
566 microarchitectural quantification of the trabecular bone was performed using the SCANCO
567 Evaluation Software (SCANCO Medical AG) with a voxel size of 8.4 μ m.

568

569 **RNA sequencing**

570 RNA sequencing was performed by Novogene Co., Ltd (Cambridge, United Kingdom) on an
571 Illumina NovaSeq platform using a paired-end 150 bp sequencing strategy. Quality assessment
572 and gene mapping were also performed by Novogene Co., Ltd (Cambridge, United Kingdom).
573 Briefly, reads pairs in FASTQ format were quality assessed by FastQC v0.11.5 and mapped to
574 murine genome (GRCm38/mm10). On average, 41% of raw reads were uniquely mapped.
575 Uniquely mapped reads were assigned to annotated genes with Tophat software (Johns Hopkins
576 University). Read counts were normalized by trimmed mean of M values (TMM) method.
577 Principal component analysis (PCA) plots, heatmaps, and volcano plots and bubble plots were

578 generated with *ggplot2*, *pheatmap*, *EnhancedVolcano*⁷⁷ R packages. Differential gene expres-
579 sion analysis was performed by using R package *edgeR* with Quasi-likelihood F-tests for sta-
580 tistical significance and following thresholds for the identification of differential expression
581 genes (DEGs): false discovery rate-corrected q value < 0.05 and fold change > 1.5 (for Thiamet-
582 G treated cells) or 2 (for OSMI-1 treated cells). DEGs were subsequently used for gene ontology
583 (GO) gene functional analysis with *clusterProfiler* package⁷⁸. Gene ratios of selected GO terms
584 were plotted as bubble plots. Gene set enrichment analysis (GSEA) was performed using the
585 GSEA software version 4.0.3 (Broad Institute) with a threshold of 0.25 for false discovery rate-
586 corrected q value⁷⁹. The curated gene sets for GSEA were downloaded from Bader Lab⁸⁰ (re-
587 lease April 01 2020), which contains pathways from GO biological process⁸¹, Reactome⁸², Pan-
588 ther⁸³, NetPath⁸⁴, NCI⁸⁵, MSigDB⁸⁶ (C2, H collections). Gene sets from GSE10500⁸⁷ and a
589 published gene set for osteoclast differentiation³⁶ were also included for GSEA analysis.

590 To identify distinct genes at different stages of osteoclast differentiation, we analyzed the mi-
591 croarray data from the previous study (accession number GSE138324)³⁴ by the web tool
592 GEO2R (NCBI). The unique DEGs at different time points of differentiation were identified
593 with the threshold of p-value > 0.05 and fold change > 1.5. The DEGs from microarray were
594 further matched to our RNA sequencing data and visualized by heatmaps. To compare the tran-
595 scriptome of osteoclasts with OSMI-1 treatment with those of MYC knockout osteoclasts, we
596 employed the RNA-Seq data created by Bae et al. (accession number SRP096890) and analyzed
597 as described above³⁸.

598 The information of DEGs was submitted to Ingenuity Pathway Analysis (Qiagen) for upstream
599 regulator analysis. To perform the motif enrichment analyses, the upstream sequences of DEGs
600 were retrieved by RSAT tools⁸⁸ then analyzed by *matrix-scan*⁸⁹ and *AME*⁹⁰ with motifs re-
601 trieved from JASPAR (2020) and ENCODE (2018-03) databases. Random sequences generated
602 based on the upstream sequences were used as the background model for the motif enrichment
603 analyses.

604

605 **Identification of O-GlcNAcylated proteins by mass spectrometry**

606 Mass spectrometry with O-GlcNAcylated protein was performed as described⁹¹. Briefly, whole
607 cell lysates were collected from RAW264.7 cells treated with RANKL and TNF α . O-Glc-
608 NAcyated protein was further enriched by using Protein A/G agarose beads (Santa Cruz Bio-
609 technology) coupled with antibodies against O-GlcNAc (Invitrogen, clone RL2). Following
610 elution with 2 \times Lämmli buffer, the enriched protein was separated by SDS-PAGE and visual-
611 ized by InstantBlue Coomassie staining (Abcam). The protein was in-gel digested with trypsin
612 (Roche), extracted with 70% acetonitrile, 0.03% formic acid, lyophilized, and resuspended in
613 0.1% TFA (Trifluoroacetic acid). NanoLC-ESI-MS/MS experiments were performed on an Ul-
614 timate 3000 nano-RSLC (Thermo Fisher Scientific) coupled to a Q-Exactive HF-X mass spec-
615 trometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific) using a Nanospray-Flex ion source (Thermo Fisher Scien-
616 tific). Peptides were concentrated and desalted on a trap column (5 mm x 30 μ m, Thermo Fisher
617 Scientific) and separated on a 25 cm x 75 μ m nanoEase MZ HSS T3 reversed phase column
618 (100 \AA pore size, 1.8 μ m particle size, Waters, USA) operating at constant temperature of 35
619 $^{\circ}$ C. Peptides were separated at a flow rate of 300 nL/min with the following gradient profile: 2
620 % - 15 % solvent B in 37 min, 15 % - 30 % solvent B in 30 min, 30 % - 45 % solvent B in 23
621 min, 45 % - 95 % solvent B in 20 min, isocratic at 95 % solvent B for 15 min and 95 % - 2 %
622 solvent B in 5 min. Solvents used were 0.1 % formic acid (solvent A) and 0.1 % formic acid in
623 acetonitrile/H₂O (80/20, v/v, solvent B).

624 The Q Exactive HF-X was operated under the control of XCalibur 4.1.31.9 software. MS spec-
625 tra (m/z = 300-1800) were detected in the Orbitrap at a resolution of 60000 (m/z = 200) using
626 a maximum injection time (MIT) of 100 ms and an automatic gain control (AGC) value of 1 x
627 10⁶. Internal calibration of the Orbitrap analyzer was performed using lock-mass ions from
628 ambient air as described⁹². The 30 most abundant peptide precursor signals per MS scan were

629 selected for MS/MS analysis. Peptides were fragmented using high energy collision dissocia-
630 tion (HCD) at a normalized collision energy of 27 and subsequently analyzed in the Orbitrap at
631 a resolution of 15000. Further settings for MS/MS spectra included an isolation width of 1.6
632 Da, a MIT of 100 ms and an AGC value of 5×10^5 . The dynamic exclusion was set to 20 sec.
633 The protein was identified using the Mascot 2.6.1 software (Matrix Science, London, UK).
634 Spectra were searched against the mouse reference proteome sequence downloaded in FASTA-
635 format from UniProt⁹³. Search parameters specified trypsin as cleaving enzyme with three ac-
636 cepted missed cleavages, a 5 ppm mass tolerance for peptide precursors and 0.02 Da for frag-
637 ment ions. Carbamidomethylation of cysteine residues was defined as fixed modification. Me-
638 thionine oxidation, S,T,Y phosphorylation, and O-HexNAc-glycosylation at S and T were con-
639 sidered as variable modifications. Quantitative analysis was done by Scaffold 4.10 software
640 (Proteome Software, Protland, USA) with a threshold of peptide probability > 65% and a spec-
641 trum counting method. Selected O-glycopeptides were further inspected manually. Neutral loss
642 *N*-acetylglucosamine and the O-GlcNAc oxonium ion ($m/z = 204.086$) was used as O-GlcNAc
643 diagnostic marker.

644

645 **Determine O-GlcNAc levels on NUP153 by immunoprecipitation**

646 Whole cell lysates from *in vitro* osteoclastogenesis were collected in Cell Lysis Buffer (Cell
647 Signaling Technology) either two (early) or four (late) days after first RANKL stimulation.
648 Following pre-clearing, 50 μg of the lysates were incubated with 0.5 μg antibodies against
649 NUP153 (Santa Cruz Biotechnology, clone R3G1) or NFATc1 (BioLegend, clone 7A6) and
650 pulled down by Protein A/G agarose beads (Santa Santa Cruz Biotechnology). After elution
651 with $2\times$ Lämmli buffer, O-GlcNAc levels were determined by Western blot. Images were ana-
652 lyzed by Image Lab software (Bio-Rad Laboratories, version 6.0.1) with levels normalized to
653 MCSF-treated cells at individual time points.

654

655 **Assessment of nuclear accumulation of MYC in osteoclast precursors**

656 RAW264.7 cells were transfected with *Nup153* siRNA and costimulated with RANKL and
657 TNF α as described. To determine the level of chromatin-bound MYC, lysate was collected 2
658 days after the stimulation. The chromatin-bound fraction was obtained using a Subcellular Pro-
659 tein Fractionation kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific) and subjected to Western blot analysis.
660 The nuclear levels of MYC were evaluated by immunofluorescence staining using anti-MYC
661 (Cell Signaling Technology, clone D84C12), anti-NUP153 (Santa Cruz Biotechnology), and
662 DAPI. Images were acquired using CellInsight CX5 High Content Screening Platform with
663 Colocalization.V4 BioApplication (Thermo Fisher Scientific) for cellomics analysis and Leica
664 SP5 II confocal laser scanning microscope (Leica Microsystems) for confocal microscopy. Nu-
665 clear volume was identified from the confocal images by an ImageJ plugin *Colocalization Im-*
666 *age Creator* with Otsu thresholding on DAPI signal. The nuclear MYC and perinuclear
667 NUP153 was quantified by ImageJ plugin *MorphoLibJ*^{94,95}.

668

669 **RNAi and osteoclastogenesis on RAW264.7**

670 *Nup153* knockdown was achieved by transfecting *Nup153* siRNA (Thermo Fisher Scientific)
671 with Lipofectamine RNAiMAX (Thermo Fisher Scientific) reagent following the manufac-
672 turer's instruction. RAW264.7 cells were incubated overnight for post-transfection recovery.
673 Cells were treated with 100 ng/mL RANKL (Peprotech) and 20 ng/mL TNF α (R&D Systems)
674 to trigger osteoclastogenesis. The culture medium was changed every 2 days. Mature osteo-
675 clasts could be found after 4 days of RANKL stimulation.

676

677 **Regulation of *Ogt* and *Oga* upon RANKL and TNF α costimulation**

678 To determine the initial response triggered by osteoclastogenic stimulation, bone marrow-de-
679 rived cells were pre-treated with 1 μ M SB202190 (Tocris), 5 μ M of FR180204 (Tocris), 1 μ M
680 SU6656 (Selleck Chemicals), 40 μ M T-5224 (ApexBio Technology), or vehicle 2 hours before

681 osteoclastogenic stimulation. Cells were lysed after 6 hours of RANKL+TNF α costimulation,
682 and the *Ogt* and *Oga* mRNA levels were measured by quantitative real-time PCR.

683

684 **Statistics**

685 The results are presented as median \pm interquartile range (IQR), if not stated elsewhere. The
686 sample sizes (n) are shown in the figure legends. Quantification of cellomics data is shown as
687 violin-histograms, in which the violin graph shows the data distribution within the group, and
688 the histogram shows the proportion of the data from the whole dataset. Mann-Whitney U-tests
689 were applied for the comparison between two groups. ANOVA was applied for multiple com-
690 parisons within more than two groups. The post hoc analysis was performed with the Bonferroni
691 method. *P*-values lower than 0.05 were considered statistical significant. All graphs and statis-
692 tics were generated using Prism9 (GraphPad Software) and the R software (version 3.6.1) with
693 *tidyverse* and *see* packages.

694

695 **Study approval**

696 This study was approved by the ethical committee of the University of Erlangen-Nürnberg. All
697 patients recruited in this study signed informed consent. The animal experiments were approved
698 by the regional government (Regierung von Unterfranken, Würzburg, Germany).

699

700 **Data and materials availability**

701 The information of data generated and analyzed during this study are available from the corre-
702 sponding author on request.

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724

725 **Conflict of interest statement**

726 Although none of the authors has any direct conflict of interest related to O-GlcNAcylation in
727 osteoclasts, J.H.W.D. are involved in the development of new targeted therapies for fibrotic
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734

735 **Author contributions**

736 Y.-N.L., C.-W.C., T.T.-M., A.-E.M., J.P., and J.H.W.D. designed the research. Y.-N.L., C.-
737 W.C., T.T.-M., P.H., X.D., C.T.M., X.X., C.L., V.F., R.L., K.H, and N.-Y.L. performed the
738 experiments. A.-E.M., A.-H.G., F.K., and J.H.W.D. retrieved and interpreted the clinical data.
739 Y.-N.L., C.-W.C., T.T.-M., H.Z., A.-E.M., P.H., M.-C.H., J.P., A.R., and J.H.W.D analyzed
740 and interpreted the results. Y.-N.L., C.-W.C., G.S., and J.H.W.D. wrote the manuscript.

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958 **Fig. 1 Dynamic regulation of protein O-GlcNacylation during osteoclastogenesis.**

959 (A) Western blot analysis of protein O-GlcNacylation during osteoclastogenesis *in vitro* (n =
960 4 per group). Representative images and quantification of the changes in the levels of O-
961 GlcNAc normalized to β -actin over time are shown. (B) Representative Voronoi-tessellated
962 cellomics images of *in vitro* osteoclastogenesis and cellomics analysis of O-GlcNacylation

963 levels in immature and mature osteoclasts (OC) (n = 21025 cells in total). **(C and D)**
964 Representative histology and confocal microscopic images of O-GlcNAc, TRAP and CD14
965 triple stainings in bone tissues from healthy donors and RA patients **(C)** or wildtype and hTNF α
966 tg mice **(D)**. Semi-automated, blinded quantification of O-GlcNAcylation in immature and
967 mature OC in synovial tissue sections (n = 10 sections per group). Immature OC (green) and
968 mature OC (yellow) are marked with arrows. **(E)** Representative blots of Western blots and
969 ProteinSimple Wes immunoassay of O-GlcNAcylation, OGT and OGA expression (n = 4 per
970 group). **(F)** Representative cellomics images of protein O-GlcNAcylation in immature OC and
971 its correlation (Spearman) with osteoclastogenesis. The OC fusion index represents the
972 proportion of the nuclei in mature OCs (n = 9 per group).

973 Bar graphs are shown as median \pm IQR. Linear regression and its 95% confidence interval
974 (dashed line) are presented in the correlation plots **(F)**. Horizontal scale bars are represented as
975 50 μ m in IF images or 200 μ m in H&E images. Statistical significance was determined by
976 Mann-Whitney U-test **(A, B, E)** or two-way ANOVA **(C and D)**. *P*-values and Spearman's ρ
977 are shown in the graphs. AUC, area under the curve; OC, osteoclast; MFI, mean fluorescence
978 intensity.

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Fig. 2 Pharmacological inhibition of OGT arrests osteoclastogenesis at early stages of differentiation.

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(A and B) Western blot analysis (A), representative images of high-content imaging, and cellomics analysis (B) of O-GlcNAcylation during *in vitro* osteoclastogenesis in the presence of TNF α and with or without OSMI-1 (n = 5 per group for western blot; n = 11759 cells in total for cellomics). (C) Levels of osteoclast-related genes analyzed by real-time PCR after OSMI-1 treatment (n = 4 per group). (D) Representative images of high-content imaging and the cellomics analysis of the proportions of immature and mature osteoclasts, the OC fusion index, and TRAP enzyme activity (n = 102666 cells in total). (E) Proliferation assay (n = 4 per group). (F) *In vitro* bone resorption assay with OSMI-1 treatment (n = 6 per group).

990 All bar graphs are shown as median \pm IQR. Horizontal scale bars are represented as 50 μm in
991 IF images, 100 μm in bone resorption assay. Statistical significance was determined by Mann-
992 Whitney U-test (**A and B**) or two-way ANOVA (**C to F**). *P*-values are shown in the graphs.
993 AUC, area under the curve; MFI, mean fluorescence intensity, OC, osteoclast.

994

995 **Fig. 3 Pharmacological inhibition of OGA impairs osteoclast maturation.**

996 (A and B) Western blot analysis (A), representative images of high-content imaging, and
 997 cellomics analysis (B) of O-GlcNAcylation during *in vitro* osteoclastogenesis in the presence
 998 of TNF α and with or without Thiamet-G (TG) (n = 5 per group for western blot; n = 17973
 999 cells in total for cellomics). (C) mRNA levels of osteoclast-related genes (n = 4 per group). (D)
 1000 Representative images of high-content imaging and cellomics analysis of the proportions of
 1001 immature and mature OC, OC fusion index, and TRAP enzyme activity (n=142807 cells in
 1002 total). (E) Proliferation assay (n = 6 per group). (F) *In vitro* bone resorption assay (n= 4 per
 1003 group).

1004 All bar graphs are shown as median \pm IQR. Horizontal scale bars are represented as 50 μm in
1005 IF images, 100 μm in bone resorption assay. Statistical significance was determined by Mann-
1006 Whitney U-test (**A and B**) or two-way ANOVA (**C to F**). *P*-values are shown in the graphs.
1007 AUC, area under the curve; MFI, mean fluorescence intensity, OC, osteoclast.

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Fig. 4 Pharmacological inhibition of OGT ameliorates bone loss in serum-induced arthritis.

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(A) Grip strength and joint swelling in mice serum-induced arthritis (SIA) treated with OSMI-1. (B) Representative images and quantification of microcomputed tomography scans of bone

1013 tissue and analysis of the tibial bone structure. **(C)** Representative histological and confocal
1014 microscopy images of the tarsus with semi-automated, blinded quantification of H&E staining,
1015 TRAP staining, and O-GlcNAcylation. ($n \geq 4$ for all groups).

1016 All results are presented as median \pm IQR. Horizontal scale bars are represented as 50 μm in
1017 IF images, 100 μm in histological staining. Statistical significance was determined by two-way
1018 ANOVA (**A and C**) or Mann-Whitney U-test (**B**). *P*-values are shown in the graphs. MFI, mean
1019 fluorescence intensity, OC, osteoclast.

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1021 **Fig. 5 Pharmacological inhibition of OGA ameliorates bone loss in human TNF α**

1022 **transgene mice.**

1023 (A) Grip strength and joint swelling in hTNF α tg mice treated with Thiamet-G (TG). (B) Images
 1024 and quantification of microcomputed tomography scans of bone tissue and analysis of the tibial

1025 bone structure. **(C)** Representative histological and confocal images of the tarsus with semi-
1026 automated, blinded quantification of H&E staining, TRAP staining, and O-GlcNAcylation. (n
1027 ≥ 5 for all groups)

1028 All results are presented as median \pm IQR. Horizontal scale bars are represented as 50 μm in IF
1029 images, 100 μm in histological staining. Statistical significance was determined by two-way
1030 ANOVA (**A and C**) or Mann-Whitney U-test (**B**). *P*-values are shown in the graphs. MFI, mean
1031 fluorescence intensity, OC, osteoclast.

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Fig. 6 Differential transcriptomic effects of OGT and OGA inhibition during osteoclastogenesis.

1035 RNASeq of osteoclast precursor cells with inhibition of OGT by OSMI-1 or inhibition of OGA
1036 by Thiamet-G of osteoclastogenesis with respective controls, n = 3 for each condition. (A) PCA
1037 analysis demonstrating an arrest at different stages by OSMI-1 and Thiamet-G. (B) Expression
1038 heatmap of genes implicated in osteoclastogenesis by integration of publically available
1039 transcriptome data from different stages of osteoclastogenesis (GSE138324)³⁴.

1040 **OSMI-1 treatment:** (C) Volcano plot of DEGs. Expression of each gene is plotted as log-fold
1041 change of expression ratio with respect to controls; upregulated and downregulated genes are
1042 represented by red and green dots, respectively. (D) GSEA enrichment plot for osteoclast dif-
1043 ferentiation. (G) Geneset functional analysis plots of significantly enriched Gene Ontology
1044 (GO) biological processes related to osteoclastogenesis. Upward and downward triangles indi-
1045 cate the processes enriched in up- and down-regulated genes, respectively. (E, F and H)
1046 **Thiamet-G treatment:** (E) Volcano plot of DEGs. (F) GSEA enrichment plot for osteoclast
1047 differentiation. (H) Geneset functional analysis plots of the significantly enriched GO biologi-
1048 cal processes related to osteoclastogenesis.

1052 **Fig. 7 O-GlcNAcylation target NUP153 is essential for MYC nuclear accumulation and**
1053 **osteoclastogenesis.**

1054 (A) Levels of O-GlcNAcylation on NUP153 in early and late stages of osteoclastogenesis by
1055 immunoprecipitation (n = 6 per group). (B) MS2 spectrum of O-GlcNAcylated peptide in
1056 NUP153 from RANKL and TNF α costimulated RAW264.7 cells. (C) Western blot analysis for
1057 chromatin bound MYC in the cells with *Nup153* knockdown or OSMI-1 (n = 3 replicates). (D)
1058 Representative immunofluorescence images of confocal microscopy and quantification of the
1059 median MYC intensity within the nuclear volume in the cells treated with OSMI-1 and *Nup153*
1060 siRNA (n \geq 30 cells per group). Spearman correlation analysis on the intensities of MYC and
1061 NUP153 in cells treated with *Nup153* siRNA (n = 20 cells). (C and D) Unless specified, cells
1062 were treated with vehicle and non-targeting siRNA. (E) Representative images for TRAP stain-
1063 ing on cells transfected with *Nup153* siRNA. (F) Conceptual scheme of the functional role of
1064 O-GlcNAcylation modulation of NUP153 during osteoclastogenesis. The illustration was cre-
1065 ated by using images from Servier Medical Art (<http://smart.servier.com/>) and Scheng23
1066 (https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:O-GlcNAc_cycling-1.png), licensed under CC BY 3.0
1067 (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/>) and CC BY-SA 4.0 licenses (<https://crea->
1068 [tativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/)), respectively.

1069 Bar graphs are shown as median \pm IQR. Horizontal scale bars represent 5 μ m (D) or 50 μ m
1070 (E) in IF images. Statistical significance was determined by two-way (A) or one-way
1071 ANOVA (C and D). *P*-values and Spearman's ρ are presented in the graphs. Linear
1072 regression and its 95% confidence interval (dashed line) are presented in the correlation plots
1073 (D). MFI, median fluorescence intensity.